
ANALYSIS OF SPEECH SIGNALS FOR AUTOMATIC RECOGNITION

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Abstract: Automatic speech recognition is the process of turning a speech signal into a meaningful message (its corresponding text). Automatic speech recognition is a pattern recognition application, so it needs to extract useful features from its input signal. Several acoustic analyses to extract the features are described in this paper. The most widely used set of these feature vectors is the Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients and it is used in the traditional front end analysis in speech recognition (MFCC). They are based on a typical power spectrum estimate that has been decorrelated using a modified discrete cosine transform after first undergoing a log-based transform of the frequency axis (Mel-frequency scale). There is also discussion of further speech analysis methods as the Short Time Fourier Transform (STFT), linear predictive analysis and dynamic feature extraction. The speech sample is roughly represented as a linear mixture of prior speech samples in linear predictive analysis.

Key words: feature extraction, cepstral coefficients, linear prediction, speech perception, speech recognition

INTRODUCTION

Information is sent from a speaker to one or more listeners through speech. Pressure waves generated by the speaker and transmitted from the mouth to the ears of the listener constitute the speech signal. The major sound source, the mouth, is monitored directly in front of the signal which is fluctuations in pressure as a function of time. Automatic speech recognition is the process of turning a speech signal into a meaningful message (its matching text). Speech recognition is the process of using a computer program to turn spoken words into a sequence. Speech recognition has a wide range of uses, but some common ones are voice dialing, call rerouting, data entry and dictation, command and control and computer-assisted language acquisition. These contemporary systems often have statistical models at their core including hidden markov models (HMMs). The popularity of HMM can be attributed, in part, to the fact that its parameters can be computed, are simple, and can be automatically estimated from a vast quantity of data. Three stages are involved in the creation of speech: sound

excitation generation, vocal tract articulation and radiation from the lips or nostrils. If the stimulus is a quasi-periodic train of air pressure pulses produced by the vibration of the vocal chords, the result is a voiced sound. The vocal tract must first be restricted, typically toward the mouth end, in order to produce unvoiced sounds. Then, we produce turbulence by forcing air through the obstruction quickly enough. The excitation that results has a waveform that looks like broadband noise. The excitation's spectrum is shaped by the vocal tract tube, which has a frequency response resonant with that of wind instruments or organ pipes. The vocal tract tube resonates at formant frequencies, also known as formants. The vocal tract's shape can produce a variety of sounds because it affects its frequency response. We usually presume that the vocal tract's anatomy remains nearly constant across intervals of roughly 10 milliseconds since it changes gradually during continuous speech. Speech is made up of a succession of sounds that are produced at a pace of roughly 12 per second. Speech is often broken up into successive sets of samples for proper processing. If these segments are too long, analysis will generate unexpected results and result in ASR classification mistakes. Too little time can allow noise to take control. A common choice for windows is a 25ms hamming window. More details about the speech spectrum are necessary in order to categorize the phonemes. The input for a modification of the standard short-time DFT is most typically a windowed slice of speech. This procedure is repeated periodically by shifting the window for consecutive frames, converting the complete signal into a set of DFTs. One well-liked methodology for huge data reduction for speech applications is the linear predictive coding technique, which imposes a speech-specific model of speech creation. Today's typical method for ASR analysis is Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients, a cutting-edge speech analysis method that took the role of linear predictive analysis in the 1980s. Obtaining the speech spectral power is the initial stage, which is frequently done using an N-point DFT but sporadically using LP. By multiplying this collection of N spectral powers (indexed on frequency) by a series of (isosceles) triangle functions that approximate the Bark or Mel scale, the N samples are then converted into typically 20–24 energy values, as in the number of significant bands. Then a logarithm is used to apply the decibel conversion. The last step to get the MFCC is an inverted cosine (DCT) transform. Before speech reaches the ASR input microphone, speech is typically corrupted in various real-world circumstances, for instance by channel distortions or background noise. The efficiency of the analysis methods discussed above varies in various situations, and ASR that uses methods that are less resistant to degradations suffers from inferior accuracy. How to modify ASR to handle the wide variety of variations seen in varied speech contexts is a key topic of research.

SPEECH PRODUCTION AND PERCEPTION

Transferring ideas is the goal of human verbal communication. The speaker's brain generates the concepts, which are then translated into speech signals by the human vocal system. The speech signal is subsequently transmitted to the listener via air, where it may be influenced by outside noise sources. The transmission is complete when the acoustical signal is registered by the human auditory system and the listener's brain begins to interpret this waveform to comprehend its content. Air pressure waves that come from the speaker's mouth and nose create speech. Lungs, larynx, nose, and various mouth components are the primary organs involved in the creation of speech. A speech generation model that simulates the resonance properties of the vocal tract by sending a glottal excitation waveform through a time-varying linear filter can be used to represent speech signals. The glottal excitation can be presumed to be in one of two states, which correspond to voiced or unvoiced speech, in many speech applications.

Fig 1. Binary model for speech production

Fig 2. Source channel model for a speech recognition system

The goal of voice recognition software is to emulate the human speech communication system. Figure depicts a source-channel model for a voice recognition system. The peripheral auditory system breaks down the received acoustic pressure signal into two phases: first, it creates a mechanical vibration pattern on the basilar membrane; second, it represents the pattern as a series of pulses that will be relayed by

the auditory nerve. Lastly, the perceptual information is extracted by the auditory nerve system. The eardrum vibrates at the same frequency as the sound pressure wave when it is exposed to sound. The middle ear is used to transmit the vibrations. The cochlea, which connects to the auditory nerve and is the primary component of the inner ear, transmits a representation of sound to the brain. The cochlea can be thought of as a filter bank with outputs arranged according to location, allowing for the conversion of frequencies into locations. The filters closest to the base of the cochlea respond to higher frequencies, whereas those closest to the apex of the cochlea respond to lower frequencies.

SPEECH RECOGNITION SYSTEM

Speech recognition is the ability to hear spoken words, distinguish between the different sounds they include, and identify them as words from a particular language. The ability of computer systems to absorb spoken words in audio formats like wav or raw and then produce their content in text format may thus be classified as speech recognition in the realm of computer systems.

Fig 3. Speech Recognition System

In the world of computers, speech recognition entails a number of procedures and the problems that go along with them. Voice recording, word boundary detection, feature extraction, and identification with the use of knowledge models are the procedures needed to get computers to recognize speech. The process of locating the beginning and end of a spoken word in a given sound stream is known as word boundary detection. Identifying the word boundary when analyzing the acoustic stream can occasionally be challenging. This can be related to different accents people have, such as the length of the pauses they make while speaking in between each word. The process of converting a sound signal into a format usable by the subsequent phases is referred to as feature extraction. Parameters including signal amplitude, frequency energy, and other values may be extracted as part of the feature extraction process.

Recognition entails translating the input (presented in the form of different attributes) into one of the recognized sounds. To ensure accurate identification and ambiguity reduction, this may require the usage of several knowledge models. Knowledge models are models that assist the recognition system, such as phone acoustic models and language models. One must train the system in order to produce the knowledge model. One must demonstrate to the system a collection of inputs and the outputs to which they should map throughout the training phase. It's common to refer to this as supervised learning. A recognition system consists of the following parts: acoustic and linguistic models, feature extraction, speech recognition, sound recording, and word detection.

SPEECH ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES

Both time-domain and frequency-domain speech analysis techniques are examined in this section. To obtain a more useful parameterized representation of the speech signal, one that effectively conveys important information. The simplest feature to get is overall energy, which is crucial for applications like low-rate coding and speech activity recognition. Little time to acquire the energy spectrum of the voice stream, a Fourier transform is used. The speech features are estimated using Mel-Frequency Cepstral analysis and linear prediction. Due to its higher accuracy compared to linear predictive analysis, MFCC is the most used method. Similar to the conventional spectrum technique, Fourier analysis gives a voice representation as a function of frequency in terms of amplitude and phase. The magnitude of the waveform's Fourier Transform after it has been multiplied by an appropriate duration time window function is the short-time spectrum of the signal. The function to be transformed is simply multiplied in the continuous-time example by a window function that is nonzero for a brief period of time. As the window is moved along the time axis, the resulting signal's Fourier transform is computed, producing a two-dimensional representation of the signal. The conventional short-time DFT, with input being a windowed portion of speech, can be applied to speech processing. By moving the window for subsequent frames, this step is repeated on a regular basis, turning the entire signal into a collection of DFTs. The Hamming window provides a superior frequency resolution, although one might infer that rectangular windows are preferable for better stationary resolution. In reality, the Hamming window is used with window lengths of about 20 to 30 ms. This decision strikes a balance between the frequency resolution and the stationary assumption for each frame. Then, a grey scale is often used to express the energy in each time or frequency point, with white being low energy and black denoting high energy.

Fig 4. Spectrogram (a) of the speech waveform (b)

A color scale can sometimes be used to illustrate spectrograms, as in figure 4, where the deepest blue regions correspond to low energy and the lightest red parts to high energy. The majority of ASR analysis is frame-by-frame, using a brief time window—often Hamming, with a period of roughly 25 ms—to repeatedly supply the speech data for further studies. The resulting parameter vectors can be organized into a matrix, or spectrogram, with the other axis being either frequency or another related dimension, and the results plotted as a function of time (e.g., LPC order, MFCC index). Recent research has looked at several ways to improve ASR's use of the time-frequency plane.

CONCLUSION

The short time Fourier transform, linear predictive analysis, analysis of Mel-frequency cepstral coefficients, dynamic features and two-dimensional analysis are only a few of the speech analysis and feature extraction techniques covered in this study. There is a brief discussion of the theory of speech production and perceptions. Also implemented is a source channel model for the ASR system. There is a contrast between MFCC and LPC. Due to the filter bank analysis's reduced spectral resolution and subsequent truncation into MFCC components, a significant amount of pertinent information was lost during the MFCC extraction procedure. However, that allowed recovering a smoothed spectral representation in which phonetically irrelevant detail had been removed. But MFCC overtook linear predictive analysis because of its high accuracy. That did enable the recovery of a smoothed, phonetically irrelevant detail-free spectral representation. However, because to MFCC's great accuracy, it surpassed linear predictive analysis.

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